

EXPERIMENTAL SIMULATION OF A COMPOSITE COLUMN WITH A FOLLOWER FORCE

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ABSTRACT

Based on the authors' previous investigations on nonconservative problems, a simple experimental model simulating a composite cantilever with a tangential follower force is developed. In the experiments the difficult task of physically simulating of follower forces is accomplished indirectly.

INTRODUCTION

Owing to their desirable properties, composite materials are widely used in modern engineering structures. Thus the stability of composite structures under conservative and/or nonconservative loads becomes an important problem in engineering practice. Whereas some theoretical work in this respect has been carried out by some researchers, very few experimental studies can be found in the literature. This is because i) the realization of nonconservative follower loads is very difficult under common experimental environment; ii) the related experiments involve the destructions of the structures which is inappropriate for expensive composite materials. Therefore it is of importance to develop a simple nondestructive method for the stability experiments of composite structures under nonconservative loads.

In this study, the property that the nonconservative stability problem of end loaded follower force -Beck's column- shares frequencies and associated modes with a set of particular conservative centripetally loaded columns is used to simulate Beck's column experimentally. In this way a nonconservative problem is transformed into a set of conservative ones, and the difficult task of experimentally producing follower end force is avoided. The critical load is obtained by i) measuring a few vibrating frequencies of the centripetal-load model with appropriate values of load and its centripetal radius; ii) employing a curve fitting procedure for the finite number of experimental data; iii) estimating the onset of loss stability for Beck's column from the fitted curve. In this way the destruction of the test specimens is avoided.

Several glass fibre reinforced plastics specimens are tested and satisfactory results are obtained in this study.

BECK'S COLUMN AND A CENTRIPETAL LOAD MODEL

Beck's column is a cantilevered elastic column subjected to a tangential follower force at its free end, as shown in Fig.1. The analytical solution to this problem was obtained by Beck[1] in 1952 using dynamic criteria based on the Euler beam theory, which results in an eigensolution problem with the following characteristic equation:

$$J_b(\lambda, \Omega^2) = 2\Omega^2(1 + \text{ch } \beta_1 \cos \beta_2) + \lambda \Omega \text{sh } \beta_1 \sin \beta_2 + \lambda^2 = 0 \quad (1)$$

where λ and Ω^2 are the nondimensional load and frequency, respectively, i. e.

$$\lambda = pl^2/\pi^2 EI, \quad \Omega^2 = \omega^2 \rho Al^4/\pi^4 EI \quad (2)$$

and

$$\beta_1 = [(\Omega^2 + \lambda^2/4)^2 - \lambda/2]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \beta_2 = [(\Omega^2 + \lambda^2/4)^2 + \lambda/2]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

and other symbols have their conventional meanings. The eigenfrequencies of the problem with different values of load can easily be obtained from Eq.(1).

The centripetal load model is the same cantilevered column subjected to a centripetal load, i. e. the line of action of the load always passes through a fixed point on the undeformed axis the distance from which to the free end is denoted by r , as shown in Fig.2. This is a conservative problem, and its characteristic equation takes the following form[5]

$$J_c(\lambda, \Omega^2, r/l) = (2\Omega^2 + \lambda^2)(1 + \text{ch } \beta_1 \cos \beta_2) - \lambda^2 - \lambda \Omega \text{sh } \beta_1 \sin \beta_2 - \lambda(\beta_1^2 + \beta_2^2) \left(\frac{1}{\beta_1} \text{sh } \beta_1 \cos \beta_2 - \frac{1}{\beta_2} \text{ch } \beta_1 \sin \beta_2 \right) / (r/l) = 0 \quad (3)$$

where r/l is a variable parameter.

It is shown by the authors[5] that the two systems described above share one eigensolution if the centripetal radius r satisfies

$$\frac{r}{l} = \frac{\text{ch } \beta_1 - M \text{sh } \beta_1 - \cos \beta_2 + N \sin \beta_2}{\beta_1 \text{sh } \beta_1 - M \beta_1 \text{ch } \beta_1 + \beta_2 \sin \beta_2 + N \beta_2 \cos \beta_2} \quad (4)$$

where

$$M = (\beta_1^2 \text{ch } \beta_1 + \beta_1^2 \cos \beta_2) / (\beta_1^2 \text{sh } \beta_1 + \beta_1 \beta_2 \sin \beta_2), \quad N = M \beta_1 / \beta_2 \quad (5)$$

This finding is the basis of the experimental model developed in the following.

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

1. Experimental Model

Since it is much easier to realize a centripetal load in experiments than a tangential follower force, and the centripetally loaded column has relations with Beck's Column, we may obtain the experimental results for the frequencies of the latter by carrying out experiments on the former. In this way the experimental verification of Beck's column may be accomplished indirectly.

In our experiments we measured a few frequencies of the centripetally loaded column with appropriate values of the load P and the distance ratio (r/l) , which are the same as those of Beck's Column according to the analysis outlined earlier. Using the finite number of experimental data obtained we employed a curve fitting procedure. From the fitted curve the onset of loss of stability for Beck's Column was estimated.

Suppose now that the experimental characteristic equation of Beck's Column takes the following form

$$J_2(\lambda, \Omega^2, a_i) = 2a_1 \Omega^2 (a_2 + a_3 \operatorname{ch} a_4 \beta_1 \cos a_5 \beta_2) + (a_6 \lambda)(a_7 \Omega) \operatorname{sh}(a_8 \beta_1) \sin(a_9 \beta_2) + a_{10} \lambda^2 = 0 \quad (6)$$

where a_i are some undetermined constants. It is easy to see that when all of the values of a_i are unity, Eq.(6) will be the same as the exact characteristic equation (1).

Using the least squares curve-fitting method for the experimental data obtained, we may determine the values for a_i . Following this we may calculate the minimum value of load through Eq.(6) under which the first two frequencies are coincident, and this value of load may be taken as the experimental critical load for Beck's Column.

2. Experiments and Results

Five GFRP specimens were made and by simple tensile/compression tests the Young's modulus was obtained as $E = 2.238 \times 10^{10} \text{ N/m}^2$ and the mass density $\rho = 1.7011 \text{ kg/m}^3$. The geometric sizes are shown in Table1.

The centripetal load was applied by means of thin steel wires passing through a fixed point o' at a distance r from the free end, which is determined from Eq. (4). Figures 3 and 4 show the test layout. At each load application the column was given a slight vibration and the resulting frequency was measured.

Table 1. Geometric sizes of specimens (mm)

No.	1	2	3	4	5
length	295.7	297.6	297.6	298.0	297.1
width	9.92	10.40	10.40	10.40	10.34
thickness	4.66	4.64	4.64	4.54	4.52

For each of the five specimens, the nondimensional loads and frequencies were then calculated using Eq.(2) which are plotted in Fig. 5. The fitting parameters a_i in Eq.(6) were determined using the least squares curve-fitting method and the theoretical and experimental curves are also drawn in Fig. 5 for comparison.

Using the characteristic equation (6) with the parameters a_i determined, the experimental critical loads for these specimens were calculated, which are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of the experimental and theoretical critical loads (kg)

No.	1	2	3	4	5
theo.	43.82	44.31	44.31	41.83	41.28
exp.	40.15	41.16	41.01	38.91	37.19
error(%)	-8.38	-7.11	-7.44	-6.98	-9.92

CONCLUDING REMARKS

According to the authors' previous investigations on nonconservative problems, a simple experimental method simulating Beck's Column is proposed, and in effect a nonconservative problem is transformed into a set of conservative problems for experimental verification. Several glass fibre reinforced plastic specimens were tested and satisfactory results are obtained.

It is noted that for shorter columns the effect of the shear deformation would become important and thus the Timoshenko Beam theory should be used for analysis as in[6].

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Fig. 1 Beck's Column

Fig. 2 A centripetal-load model

Fig. 3 Test layout - vertical view

Fig. 4 Test layout - horizontal view

Fig. 5 Theoretical, experimental and fitting results.